

**THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE USE OF SPECIAL ACTING
GAMES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF OPERATIONAL EFFORTS IN
YOUNG WRESTLER GIRLS**

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Anatization: The young wrestler in girls are revealed to develop strength and the rapid advantage of efforts through active games in the development of operational safety.

Key words. The young wrestler is a strong run by the girls, national wrestling, bird fights, lining, circular, circle, and pulling into circulation, circularity and circulation, pulling into circulation, circulation, and pulling into circulation, circularity and circulation.

The nations of Uzbekistan have paid special attention to the spiritual, mental, moral and physical education of young people. They have been taught more national wrestling, the shooting, shooting, shooting, regularly. During the folk holidays, the warriors were particularly psychologically for fighting and individual fightings.

At the same time, in solitary confinement from the battle, it is well paid to make sure of the strength of the paver, to further improve the sense of love for the Motherland. It is known that in recent years it is also possible to know that the fact that people's physical and mental options are unlimited in the current struggle. Currently, the recorder indicator is growing rapidly, that previous conditions are not enough for the current struggle process. Mental activists grow moral, durable, conscientious, who are not afraid of any difficulties in achieving their goal.

As different types of wrestling, the wrestlers are different and the qualities of preparations for the competition.

The development of efforts in young wrestling girls is used with high opposition to develop efforts to develop power. They consists of two groups:

1. Exercise performed by external resistance. As opposition, bodies weigh from opponent's opposition, its resistance to its resistance, opposition to other bodies (in a sandy snow, thick snow and other).
2. Exercise that is performed by the possibility of the severity of its body. The exercise, which is carried out by force, has its own positive and negative aspects. The constant aspect of weight exercises is that they are easy to influence both

the large and small muscleless group and is convenient to dosage. Regional is that the speed of the action that requires strength is rapidly detected (especially in the precedence, the need to organize the exercise (especially the need for special appliance, the need for a special appliance, metal equipment. The noise and others) are visible.

The convenience of self-resistance is that shortly in large doses, it is possible to load a large dose, and it does not require special equipment and inventory, but leads to rapid loss of muscular elasticity. In addition, these exercises are performed in high nerve tension (zpr-win), so it is recommended that people are healthy and physical fitness to people, systemic controls.

In young wrestling girls, the speed of rapid efforts to develop the talent in girls, the characteristic characteristics of individuals are the concept of functional properties of the maintenance of the maintenance. There are three main forms of display of speed:

1. Individual movement speed (by winning small external resistance);
2. Frasting frequency;
3. The speed of action reaction is (the secret latent period).

Often with the maximum speed, two different phase are different:

- a) increase speed (acceleration, receipt) phase;
- b) relatively stabilization phase (acceleration in the start).

The ability to pass the distance with the ability to increase speed

As we consider, we have seen the methods of development of the operational forces in girls the ability to develop the operations of the Pupils are unique, according to this, it is advisable to choose attentive games.

First of all, the young wrestler girls need to be trained in the methods of falling and physical education activities. Of course, the development of the action skills and skills of young children is not in the teaching of the method of action. For example, in young wrestling girls, young wrestling girls need to be taught not to slow down to slow down, not to slow down before leaping before leaping them before, when they are taught to jump. The content of the game is needed to be free from small sentences in explaining the rules. Then you need to mention who stands here. Every time you do not have to explain to children, but the game rules of the game must underline the educator itself. It is advisable to show a child made frequently in fulfilling the Rule of the game. At the time of the game, the educator should not be only observers. It should be noted that the children should be converted to them and learn the complex rules, rejoicing.

During the game, it is also necessary to teach children immediately. It is important to learn that during the game, let the sign or whistle stops quickly during the game (Kapak, "Stop" or "stop"). After that, it is necessary to follow the educator's statement, his explanation. But the game should not stop much. Because it is important to remember that children will be excited in the game. The educator should also pay attention to the boundaries of the game. This is especially a very responsible time. Because the game pays little attention to time in the enjoyment. For example, wrestlers are strong, who develops a quick force, a rooster fight.

It should be noted that in the game, that the ability to show the skills of agility to hardness, and the skills of friendly support, did not follow the rule. The educator should explain the result of the educator in his own unique explanation, a beautiful analysis for children.

Development of operational efforts in young wrestler girls is the most effective methods of using the following moving games, as this is the most commonly used moving games:

- binyakmi, kugterak;
- Troubles battle;
- striping striping;
- Inputation into circle;
- casting from circle and circulation;
- run with cargo;
- Who is strong;

We see above, using moving games in the development of operational efforts in young wrestling girls gives the fruitage we expected.

References:

1. Gancharova O.V., „Yosh sportchilarni jismoniy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish”. Toshkent 2005-yil 91-100b.
2. Usmonxodjaev T.S. „Bolalar va o‘smirlar sporti mashg‘ulotlari nazariyasi va uslubiyatlari”. 2005 y. Toshkent.
3. Xo‘jaev F., Raximqulov K., B.Nigmanov. „Harakatli o‘yinlar”(o‘quv qo‘llanma)Toshkent-2006
4. Chorievna, D. Y., & Or'olovich, B. C. (2021). Opportunities to use national and movement games in physical education and athletics. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 2(05), 909-913.

5. Abduqahhorovich, S. H. (2022). INTERACTION OF SCHOOL AND FAMILY IN EDUCATION OF SCHOOL AGE CHILDREN. *Modern Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 4, 226-229.
6. Urolovich, B. C. (2021). Features of the Methods used in Physical Education. *Journal of Ethics and Diversity in International Communication*, 1(6), 88-91.
7. Dusyarov, S. (2023). EFFECTIVENESS OF ACTION GAMES IN THE PROCESS OF COMPLEX TRAINING OF YOUNG FOOTBALL PLAYERS. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2(5), 142-146.
8. O'ROLOVICH, C. B., & O'GLI, E. E. M. (2020). The Role and Effective Importance of Moving Games in the Development of the Physical Qualities of Athletes. *International Journal of Innovations in Engineering Research and Technology*, 7(10), 136-138.
9. O'GLI, E. E. M. (2020). Specific Features Of Teaching Students For Extracurricular Ball Sports. *International Journal of Innovations in Engineering Research and Technology*, 7(10), 139-141.
10. Urolovich, B. C., & Panji o'g'li, A. S. (2022). JISMONIY MADANIYAT DARSLARINI TASHKIL ETISHDA INNOVATSIYON PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH YO'LLARI. *World scientific research journal*, 4(2), 126-131.
11. NORBOYEV, A. (2023). TABLE TENNIS BENEFITS THE HUMAN BODY, CHILDREN'S HEALTH AND STRENGTHENING THE IMMUNE SYSTEM. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2(5), 150-154.
12. Urolovich, B. C., & Ugli, A. S. P. (2022). Methods of Organizing and Conducting Physical Education and Sports Events in the Daily Schedule of General Secondary School Students. *Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture*, 3(11), 242-245.
13. Boboqulov, C. (2023). EFFECTIVE USE OF GAMES IN TEACHING SKILLS TO ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2(4), 113-116.
14. Menglimurod O'g'li, E. E. (2021). Effectiveness and Advantages of using Pedagogical Technologies in Teaching Sports. *Journal of Ethics and Diversity in International Communication*, 1(6), 92-94.

